

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTERNET ADDICTION AND PSYCHOLOGICAL SYMPTOMS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract

The Internet, the most flexible and optimal means of information exchange, emerged in the middle of the 20th century and began to develop rapidly all over the world. In fact, the use of the Internet, as in many areas of society, has created favorable conditions for the computerization of training in education and the application of new training methods on this basis. It is known that the Internet is an indispensable tool that allows schoolchildren to broaden their worldview, increase cognitive capabilities, and obtain information more easily and quickly. However, along with its significant positive impact, the Internet has also created conditions for the emergence of a number of negative situations. Thus, like other modern means of communication, the Internet has caused a number of problems and led to a number of shortcomings in the system of human relations, the educational process, and in various areas of society. In this regard, studying the negative aspects of the Internet is more relevant today. Some experts point out that one of the negative aspects of the Internet is that users can easily access immoral images, texts and pornographic images. In fact, this aspect is the most obvious aspect of the problem at first glance. A comprehensive study of the problem requires penetrating into the deeper layers of its negative aspects and developing important preventive measures on this basis. Conducted psychological studies show that the most serious problem created by the Internet for schoolchildren and educational subjects is internet addiction, and Internet addiction (dependence) causes serious problems in the educational and family relationships of users, complicates the organization of educational work, and creates obstacles to the optimization of training. Thus, if a user cannot tolerate not using the Internet for a month, then we can claim that he is already facing the threat of Internet addiction. Unfortunately, this problem has been observed more often among schoolchildren recently.

Keywords: internet addiction, children, school, dependence, problems

The psychological problems caused by Internet addiction make it as dangerous as other addictions, and the implementation of the plan of measures is an important task. The development of technology not only causes a number of problems for Internet and computer users, but also increases previous problems, and causes a number of negative manifestations in the psychological plan. Despite the quick access to necessary information with the help of the Internet and its positive aspects, the advantages of the Internet overshadow the negative effects it causes.

However, it should be taken into account that virtual addiction or Internet addiction of users causes very serious socio-psychological problems, negatively affects the behavior of users, creates disharmony in their social relationships, and increases depressive states. In this regard, the study of the negative effects of the Internet and the problems it creates is very relevant for the modern era. Despite the studies conducted by psychologists and educators, it cannot be said that the problem has been completely solved. While examining the history of the study of Internet addiction in psychology, we found that the mentioned problem was studied in different directions. In psychology, Internet use and extreme deviations during use, and finally the manifestation of Internet addiction, have been evaluated as a current problem and studied in different directions.

In addition to a number of factors, the emergence of Internet addiction in schoolchildren is also seriously affected by their general health level, emotional state, self-confidence and self-awareness. In accordance with

the main hypothesis, several auxiliary hypotheses were also taken:

- There is a relationship between Internet addiction of schoolchildren and their physical health.
- There is a relationship between Internet addiction of schoolchildren and their depression.
- There is a relationship between Internet addiction of schoolchildren and their social activity.

When we talk about adolescent psychology, we first examine the characteristics of the mental development of adolescents. Thus, adolescence covers the period between childhood and adulthood. Usually, adolescence is considered as a transition stage from childhood to adulthood. In fact, adolescence can be viewed as a bridge connecting childhood and adulthood that everyone can cross. But how are the boundaries of adolescence formed? Psychologists believe that adolescence consists of 3 different stages: early adolescence (ages 11-14), middle and late adolescence (ages 15 to 18). In contrast, some researchers believe that since adolescence has its own unique characteristics, each teenager participates in this process subjectively and physiologically. development can support psychological development, but in some cases these processes are not properly completed, and thus various behavioral disorders appear.

During this age period, a fundamental change occurs in the biological maturation of the child's body. In the upper and lower extremities, the bones grow longitudinally faster than the muscles. The extremities of the body lose their proportion to the trunk and appear

longer. Height growth is very rapid, sometimes increasing by 8-10 cm in a year. In general, the development of the body in boys and girls is different at different ages. Thus, in girls, breast development begins at 10-12 years of age, after which hair appears in the genital area and under the armpits, and menstruation begins within the next 2 years. Menstrual bleeding can begin between 10-16 years of age, and irregular bleeding occurs especially in the first years. Rapid height growth occurs within 1 year after the onset of signs of puberty. Girls, who are shorter than boys on average during childhood, take their first steps towards growth at 10-12 years of age and are generally taller and heavier at this time. They reach their maximum height at 16-17 years of age.

During this age period, special changes also occur in the psychosexual development of adolescents. The onset of sexual maturation during this period plays a kind of starting point for sexual maturity. At the same time, appropriate conditions are created for psychological maturity, as well as social maturity.

In the discovery of the mechanism of adolescence, the prominent psychologist A.N. Leontiev's statement that the driving force of a child's mental development is a change in the real place he occupies in the system of social relations is of great importance [8].

There are various approaches to adolescence in the psychological literature. As we have said earlier, studying the psychological characteristics of adolescence is one of the important issues. Therefore, first of all, let us consider various approaches to adolescence. First, let us pay attention to the biological approach. According to the supporters of this point of view, the main issue in adolescence is the study of the processes of sexual maturation and physical development.

Changes in the relationships, emotional reactions, and health of adolescents are directly related to the onset of puberty.

According to biologists, the main source of the main changes is biogenetic factors. These factors play an important role in the psyche and behavior of adolescents. It is believed that the behavior of a teenager, his growth, is controlled by the internal energy of sexual maturation, and the socio-cultural conditions of his upbringing are of an insignificant nature.

One of the most prominent representatives of the theory of the biological approach is Stanley Hall. For the first time in the USA, he studied the period of adolescence, investigated its psychological characteristics. Unlike modern theorists, S. Hall believes that adolescence is a period of difficult emotional adaptation and imbalance. Frequent mood swings, apathy, self-importance and seriousness are characteristic features of a teenager [4].

One of the directions of studying the period of adolescence in its own aspect is psychoanalysis. It can be said that these directions have been analyzed at the appropriate level, unlike others. According to Freudianism, adolescence is a period of sexual maturation, excitement and manifestation of abnormal behavior. Z. Freud especially emphasizes two elements in the sexual interests of teenagers and young people: a) physical, emotional; b) mental[2].

A number of researchers have proven that the formation of personality depends not only on biological, but also on sociological and psychological factors (Margaret Mead).

One of the theories that explains a number of aspects of adolescence differently from others is social psychoanalysis. Its founder is Erik Erikson. According to him, the main feature of a teenager is his positive self-identification. This can manifest itself in identical criminal behavior.

Many researchers characterize adolescence as a "transitional period" (from childhood to youth), a "difficult period" (for teachers and parents), a "turning period" and a "crisis period". In fact, the truth is this: a child moves from one stage of his life to another, from childhood to adulthood.

We would also like to write about the contradictions that occur during adolescence. Regarding the contradictions of the adolescent personality, A. Freud noted that "Adolescents are extremely selfish, they consider themselves the center of the universe and the only being worthy of attention, but at the same time, at no later stage of their lives are they capable of such loyalty and self-sacrifice. They enter into passionate love relationships only to end them as suddenly as they began them. On the one hand, they enthusiastically join the life of society, and on the other hand, they are enveloped in a feeling of loneliness. They hesitate between blind obedience to the leader and any rebellion against authority. They They are selfish and materialistic. At the same time, they worship the sublime and idealistic. They are ascetics, but at the same time they can fall into the most primitive depression. Despite their extreme fragility, they sometimes show rudeness towards other people" [3].

A number of contradictory moments emerge in the transition from childhood to adulthood. During this age period, childhood experiences its end and a sense of adulthood begins to manifest. The transition to adulthood manifests itself from various sides. Here, a specific change in anatomical, physiological, intellectual and moral development occurs. Along with all this, serious changes are also manifested in the type of activity and living conditions of the schoolchild, and these changes create conditions for the restructuring of the psyche and the emergence of new forms of attitude towards people.

It should not be overlooked that adolescence is the most complex period of human ontogenetic development. On the one hand, this age period is a transitional period, that is, the transition from childhood to youth. At this time, a number of biological and psychophysiological changes occur in the body, and at the same time, the process of self-awareness and self-evaluation of the teenager becomes more intense. A number of contradictions manifest themselves in this process. Among such contradictions, the teenager's relatively rapid physical development, that is, the disproportionate development of body parts, and his attitude towards himself and the discrepancy between his ideas about himself plays an important role. Also, the discrepancy between the increase in his physical capabilities and his intellectual capabilities, that is, he gets tired of intellectual activity more quickly than physical movements, is

manifested. The most important thing is that despite his physical growth and intellectual development, his social position, that is, the attitude towards him (whether by parents or teachers), has not yet changed at the necessary level, he is still treated as a child, he does not believe in him properly, does not show trust.

When talking about the process of the appropriate formation of the adolescent personality, the general level of development of society, the socio-economic situation, modern historical conditions and the qualities inherent in modern adolescents, as well as individual-typological characteristics, should be taken into account. The driving forces of development during adolescence are both external contradictions occurring between the adolescent personality and the environment, and internal contradictions.

Quite diverse demands are made on the adolescent. These demands, especially when the demands of the collective do not coincide with the demands of individual people, when the environment surrounding the adolescent fundamentally differs from the school environment, a conflict arises between a teenager and the outside world. For example, if the demands made by the school to a teenager are not supported by the family, if he is given one kind of demands at school and another in the family, the conflicts between him and the teachers are resolved by slowing down, gradually weakening and abolishing old customs. Or it may be that the teenager is resolved by his own intellectual or, conversely, by the decrease in the teenager's demands on himself.

Internal conflicts cause uneven development of individual qualities and aspects of the teenager's personality. For example, the pace of perception and assimilation of knowledge is higher than the development of consciousness. Thus, a conflict arises between new knowledge and past knowledge, old ideas and new concepts, behavior and new requirements. These are not insoluble conflicts, but proper upbringing and favorable conditions resolve these conflicts.

Internal conflict can also arise between the teenager's inclinations and capabilities. For example, it happens that a teenager evaluates his own knowledge and abilities higher than they really are. Internal conflict is perceived by him as an external conflict. Correct upbringing affects him allows him to rise to the desired level. The contradiction between ability and character, between personal needs and moral duty is also of this kind.

The contradiction between the forms of cognition is also an internal contradiction. For example, if there is no unity between the teenager's feelings and logical cognition, he, as a rule, opposes his personal experience to the regular course of events, evaluates everything in terms of concrete facts. Sometimes he even goes to the extreme of opposing the knowledge he has gained as a result of personal experience to scientific knowledge. The contradiction between reason and feelings is resolved by objective analysis of facts and events and correct generalization.

Internal contradiction also arises when the natural capabilities of the teenager and the qualities he has acquired in life do not match each other. For example, a teenager with a choleric temperament type in his behavior tries to restrain his feelings, sometimes regrets when he gets excited and loses his temper, and tries to behave with restraint. Or, although a teenager with a melancholic type wants to be optimistic and courageous in all situations, his shyness and indecision prevent him from. These contradictions are resolved by strengthening the will and developing volitional qualities.

Youth Another important contradiction that is more clearly noticeable during the Melik period and is sharply expressed in its behavior and actions is the discrepancy between the teenager's desires and wishes and his social position. All these discrepancies and contradictions are reflected in one way or another in the emotional-volitional characteristics, behavior and attitudes, and the system of relationships of teenagers.

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